

INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING: REGISTER AND ACCESS TOWARDS TRANSCENDENCE AMIDST CRISIS

Joseph L. Torres

*Sto Niño High School, DepEd Tanjay City Division, Negros Oriental, Philippines
St. Paul University Dumaguete, Negros Oriental, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the instructional materials utilized by English teachers in teaching English in the Tanjay City Division of the school year 2020-2021. With the use of purposive sampling, the researcher was able to invite 72 English teachers to take part in this investigation. Furthermore, using the explanatory sequential Mixed method, the research extracted teachers' significant experiences, including their challenges and best practices in utilizing these materials from a trained teacher to avoid bias from the researcher's perspective. Moreover, the survey questionnaire was floated manually and online for the respondents' comfort. The researcher followed strict adherence to safety protocols to avoid danger from COVID-19. Concerning data analyses, percentage distribution, weighted mean, Pearson's, and Spearman Rho Correlation were utilized for quantitative purposes. On the other hand, the researcher employed thematic analysis for qualitative data extracted from focused group discussions. The results revealed that teachers in their 30s, where the majority acquired insufficient training and could not finish advanced studies, utilized much use of Instructional Materials. Furthermore, the higher the Instructional materials are used, the more available they are, and vice versa, though teachers with higher education tend to lessen the use of instructional materials. Thus, the use and availability of instructional materials can help enhance students' learning, especially when they do tasks that experience the utilization of these materials (Theory of Cone of Experience), and they can associate their experiences by connecting to the new sets of ideas and concepts (Theory of Connectionism). Moreover, more instructional materials are used and available in the Highlands than in Lowland locations.

Keywords: *Instructional Materials in English Language Teaching, Challenges and Best Practices on the Utilization of Instructional Materials, Explanatory Sequential Mixed Method*

INTRODUCTION

"Young children learn differently from old children and adults, yet we can teach them many things if we adapt our materials and mode of instruction to their level of ability, but we miseducate young children when we assume that their learning abilities are comparable to those of older children and that they can be taught with materials and with the same instructional procedures to school-age children" – (*David Elkind*). This quote is very evident in the teaching and learning process since teachers lack knowledge on how to employ certain instructional materials that are congruently relative to the student's ability. The employment of instructional materials has significantly taken importance in their role in the student's courses in education. Students' learning experiences are greatly influenced by the instructional materials they use. These resources can include worksheets, movies, textbooks, and internet sites that offer learners crucial knowledge and direction. Students' comprehension and retention of material can be significantly impacted by the caliber and applicability of their teaching resources. In this regard, the theory of connectionism by Eduard Thorndike, an American Psychologist, says that when people can establish connections between a certain stimulus and a response, they have learned something (Lee, 2018). When learners form associations through any form of instructional materials, they have a high potential to relate and can perform in class discussions. Undeniably, the role of these materials in students' Learning becomes vital, especially when students are given opportunities to experience Learning using instructional materials. In this sense, the theory of the cone of experience by Edgar Dale (1960) takes place. Edgar Dale created the Cone of Experience, popularly called the Learning Pyramid. This model demonstrates the usefulness of various learning experiences in terms of retention. Dale asserts that students are more likely to retain the material when actively involved in their education. Concrete experiences, such as hands-on activities and direct engagement, are at the base of the cone.

In terms of retention, experiences are considered the best (S. J. Lee & Reeves, 2018). This idea means that when students are allowed to use and experience these materials in class, a higher percentage of retention and Learning will be attained. It is one of the advantages of utilizing instructional materials in teaching and Learning. However, issues will inevitably be pinned on this topic. Despite their adverse effects, the scantiness of instructional materials (IMs) generally led teachers to utilize them for all types of learners. In this aspect, the theory of constraints is relevant. According to the theory that Eliyahu M. Goldratt developed in the 1980s, every system has at least one limitation that prevents it from achieving its objectives and is one of the fundamental tenets of TOC. Organizations may significantly enhance their operations and produce better results by recognizing these limits and addressing them methodically (*Theory of Constraints (TOC) / Lean Production*, n.d.). Anent to address this problem, the Department of Education (DepEd) proactively addresses this issue. DO 13, S. 2012, or the Guidelines on the

Allocation, Delivery, and Distribution of Instructional Materials (IMs) to Support the k to 12 Curriculum. It is clearly stated in this DepEd Order that The Department of Education (DepEd) has allocated funds from the Fiscal Year (FY) 2012 Textbook Funds and subsequent years until FY 2015 for the provision of the centrally procured Learning Activity Packages (LAPs), modules, and Other Instructional Materials (OIMs) to support the initial implementation of the K to 12 Curriculum. These materials will fill in the gaps in the Textbooks (TXs) and Teacher's Manuals (TMs) currently used in public elementary and secondary schools. Through this mandate, Learning can be achieved through various disciplines and strategies.

Nowadays, teachers have been using multiple tools to address learning issues among our learners in dealing with classroom issues. These strategies are proven to promote the abilities and bring the maximum potential of our learners in their respective roles in the class. These strategies include instructional materials that are utilized by teachers all over the world. These are considered sources of educational platforms such as printed materials, graphic organizers, audio, visual, audio-visual, electronic interactive, and teacher-made resources that provide timely and relevant information used in a particular course to aid learners in achieving the goal of Learning. Significantly, the instructional teaching materials make teaching and learning easier because they attract learners' attention, facilitate abstract concept understanding, save time by limiting the usage of wordy explanations, and allow learners to handle objects in the environment (Ambrocio, 2016). Some of these are multimedia tools that are also effective in delivering lessons in a classroom. Usually, these tools are animated and presented through videos (Guan et al.,2018). This static and dynamic application supports verbal instruction and comprehension (Alemdag & Cagiltay, 2018).

Furthermore, with computer-aided technology, English is no longer boring but fun. It stimulates, motivates, and encourages learners to bring their potential to the maximum level as of how learning occurs. With this advantage, these instructional materials provide knowledge and a view of the topic, including its facts and information that learners can relate to and connect to the learning process. However, utilizing these materials shall be scrutinized first to ensure the validity and effectiveness of our learner's needs, including their age and level of understanding (Bukoye, 2019). Teachers must use the right materials and knowledge for learning courses to succeed. There are a lot of tools and materials for instruction, but one must choose the ones that will fit in. In evaluating the materials, it is important to consider if these appeal to the learner, the material's credibility, validity, reliability, the ability of the materials to motivate, flexibility, and appropriateness of the material (Balachandaran, 2021).

Moreover, in preparing the content from the instructional materials, the teacher first needs to assess the student's background knowledge to have a strong foundation of contextualization. Contextualization refers to relating and presenting lessons in the context of the prevailing local environment, culture, and resources. Hence, lessons are becoming more real-life, customized, and appropriate. In this aspect, instructional materials play a vital role in developing skills among learners in the entire part of education.

Relatively, the concept of instructional materials is utilized in this paper. This study is conducted to determine the instructional materials used by English teachers teaching English during the pandemic, their demographic profile, and other variables. Moreover, this research uncovers the English teachers' challenges and their best practices in the field in the school year 2020-2021. Thus, this study specifically answered the following questions.

Research Questions

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.3 teachers' performance rating
 - 1.4 number of training days in English Language 2020-2021
2. To what extent do English teachers use the following instructional materials in terms of:
 - 2.1 printed;
 - 2.2 audio;
 - 2.3 visual;
 - 2.4 audiovisual; and
 - 2.5 teacher made resources;
3. What is the extent of availability of instructional materials utilized by English teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1 printed;
 - 3.2 audio;
 - 3.3 visual;
 - 3.4 audiovisual; and
 - 3.5 teacher made resources;
4. Is there a significant relationship between the instructional materials used by English teachers and their demographic profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of use and availability of instructional materials utilized by English teachers?
6. Is there a significant difference between the availability and the extent of use of instructional materials when respondents are grouped according to location?
7. What challenges do English teachers encounter in the utilization of instructional materials?
8. How do English teachers cope with these challenges?

Hypothesis:

1. There is no significant relationship between the Teachers' use of the instructional materials and their Demographic Profile.
2. There is no significant relationship between the extent of use and availability of instructional materials utilized by English teachers.

3. There is no significant difference between the availability of instructional materials when respondents are grouped according to location.

METHODOLOGY

This part of the study discusses the research design, research locale, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedures, and data analyses.

Research Design

The study uses an explanatory sequential mixed technique of research. The explanatory sequential design of Creswell and Plano Clark involves first gathering quantitative data and then gathering qualitative data to supplement or further explain the quantitative results (*Basic Mixed Methods Research Designs*, n.d.) This strategy is justified because, while quantitative data and results offer a general image of the study problem, further analysis, particularly through the acquisition of qualitative data, is required to enhance, extend, or clarify the overall picture. The researcher used custom-made survey questionnaires to collect quantitative data on respondents' perceptions of English teachers' availability and utilization of instructional resources.

*Explanatory Sequential Mixed Method
Creswell & Plano- Clark (2011)*

The study also looked at how readily available instructional materials were in connection to how much they were used by English teachers. It also looked to see if there was any correlation between the demographics of the instructor responses and the IMs. The study also sought to identify the difficulties and effective strategies English teachers used while utilizing educational resources. The researcher used a mixed method in this case.

Research Locale

The study concentrated on the teachers of Tanjay City Division who are teaching English. Due to the pandemic, the researcher floated the survey questionnaire to teachers via online (Google Forms) and manual approach. Moreover, the FGD was administered to English teachers representing the hinterland schools, and the other was for the lowland schools.

In disseminating the survey questionnaire, the researcher ensured that it would be convenient for the respondents to support this study. The survey form was sent through emails or messenger accounts for those who chose online and manual distribution for those who preferred it. The said approach strictly observed the safety protocol standards of IATF, such as wearing a mask and disinfecting through alcohol before distributing the survey material. So, the researcher and the participant observed social distancing as a preventive measure.

Research Respondents

The researcher included eleven English teachers from hinterland schools and sixty-one (61) from lowland schools, for a total of seventy-two English teachers-respondents of Tanjay City Division. The selection of respondents utilized a purposive sampling technique. Based on the criteria made by the researcher, all the respondents were qualified to be part of the data gathering.

Research Instrument

This study utilized both self-made survey questionnaires and guide questions. The survey questionnaire treated the quantitative data, and the guide questions were used for qualitative data utilizing Focused Group Discussions (FGD).

The Development of a self-made questionnaire underwent pilot testing and was administered at Bais City Division. It was necessary to check the reliability of the questionnaire. As a result, the Cronbach Alpha is 0.789, indicating a high-reliability level. Thus, the questionnaire is internally consistent. Validity-wise, the questionnaire was scrutinized by three English Experts in the field.

Moreover, the question guide for FGD was made based on the study objective and research questions. Through Structured questions, the interviewer can be flexible in asking and probing questions based on the respondents' responses.

Data Gathering Procedures

This study involved three steps in the data-gathering process: pre-, during, and post-gathering. The pre-data collection phase involved the researcher determining the eligibility requirements for the participants. An English teacher was trained as part of this process and would lead concentrated group discussions to avoid personal bias from the researcher's perspective. Consequently, a letter of intent and permission was sent to the Division of Office in Tanjay. After the approval, the respondents were invited for an online orientation related to the nature and scope of the study. In addition, during data collection, the researcher applied two strategies: 1) sending the survey questionnaire through Google Forms for online choice and 2) floating the survey questionnaire with the help of the school heads for those who chose the manual survey. The researcher strictly followed the safety protocols when administering the manual survey.

On the other hand, the data-gathering procedure in the qualitative aspect was made possible through an online platform like Google Meet. A trained teacher was assigned to conduct the FGD with seven English teachers until data saturation was reached in the fourth session. Moreover, the interviewer returned to each respondent for member checking to make the data credible. It was necessary to check whether the interviewer's interpretation accurately reflected the respondents' intended meaning and whether their responses were nuances and changes. Lastly, after data gathering, the researcher tallied and tabulated all the data sets for quantitative and transcribed the representatives' responses for qualitative purposes.

Data Analyses

This study employed separate analyses since a mixed method was utilized in this research.

The demographic profile of the respondents was determined using the frequency and percentage distribution as provided with the formula:

$$P = f/n \times 100\%$$

Where: P – percentage
 f – frequency
 n – number of samples

The extent use of instructional materials utilized by teachers teaching English was rated based on the quantified rating. The categories on the extent use of instructional materials utilized by teachers teaching English ranged from 1 to 5.

Extent of Use of Instructional Materials		
Scale	Verbal Description	Explanation
5	Very Much	The instructional material is used in every session
4	Much	The instructional material is used four to 5 times a week
3	Seldom	The instructional material is used 2 to 3 times a week
2	Very seldom	The instructional material is used once a week
1	Not used at all	The instructional material is never used at all

The availability of instructional materials utilized by teachers teaching English was rated based on the quantified which ranged from 1 to 5.

Availability of Instructional Materials		
Scale	Verbal Description	Explanation
5	Always	The instructional material is available in the classroom
4	Often	The instructional material is available for use twice a week
3	Sometimes	The instructional material is available for use once a week

2	Seldom	The instructional material is available for use every two weeks
1	Never	The instructional material is never found in the classroom at all.

The Weighted Mean was used in interpreting the extent and availability of instructional materials utilized by English teachers with the following formula:

$$\text{Weighted mean} = \frac{\sum wx}{\sum w}$$

where: Σ = the sum of
W = the weights
X = the value

(<https://www.statisticshowto.datasciencecentral.com/weighted-mean/>)

The challenges and good practices on teachers' utilization of instructional materials are simply the responses made by the respondents during the FGD. The trained teacher interviewed a group from hinterland and lowland schools to substantiate the result of the quantitative data. The qualitative data was interpreted through Thematic analysis (Caulfield, J. (2019) *How to Do Thematic Analysis*. - References - Scientific Research Publishing, n.d.), which is explained in the research procedure.

Pearson R Correlation will be used to determine the significant relationship between the instructional materials used by English teachers and their demographic profile with a ratio or interval variables, as well as the significant relationship between the extent of use and availability of instructional materials utilized by English teachers.

The result was interpreted as follows:

Pearson's Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation
0.00	No association between the two variables
0.01–0.19	Negligible association between the variables
0.20–0.39	Weak association between the variables
0.40–0.69	Medium association between the variables
0.70–1.00	The strong association between the variables

In determining the significant relationship between the instructional materials used by English teachers and their demographic profile with ordinal variables, the Spearman Rho Correlation was utilized.

The Significance of the Relationship using Pearson's R and Spearman Rho Correlations was ascertained by rejecting the null hypothesis that there is no relationship between the two variables when the P-value is less than the Significance Level of 0.05. The T-test was used to determine the significant difference between the availability and

the extent of use of instructional materials when respondents were grouped according to location.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results acquired during this investigation are presented in this section. This also demonstrates the use of statistical methods in the presentation, interpretation, and explanation of the data.

1. Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. 1 Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage Distribution (%)
20 – 29	25	34.72
30 - 39	28	38.89
40 - 49	16	22.22
50 – 59	3	4.17
Total	72	100.00

Table 1.1 shows that 38.89 percent of the respondents were aged 30 - 39 years old. This implies that a number of the respondents are almost in the middle part of practicing their profession as teachers.

Table 1.2 Highest Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage Distribution (%)
Bachelor's Degree	67	93.06
Masters	5	6.94
Total	72	100.00

The table above presents that 93.06 percent of the respondents had bachelor's degrees which denotes that the majority had not finished advanced studies. This implies that teachers shall continue and finish advanced studies to improve their skills and be proficient in their profession (The Importance of Professional Development for Educators, (n, d.). In addition, advanced studies such as a master's degree can improve teaching skills and increase job stability (Five Benefits of Having a Master's in Education, 2021).

Table 1.3 Teachers' Performance Rating

Performance Rating	Frequency	Percentage Distribution (%)
Outstanding	1	1.39
Very Satisfactory	71	98.61
Total	72	100.00

The table above shows that 98.61 percent of the respondents performed Very Satisfactory, meaning that most of the respondents performed better in their profession

as teachers. This idea implies that teachers are encouraged to do their best and be proficient in their profession to deliver quality education. Thus, the said goal is anchored by the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), which ensures the delivery of quality, accessible, relevant, and liberating basic education in the country. This concept is aligned with the Guidelines on Establishment and Implementation of RPMS in DepEd, which manages monitors. It measures performance and identifies human resource and organizational development needs (RPMS-PPST: Helping teachers improve the delivery of quality basic education, 2018).

Table 1.4 Number of Training Days in English Language Year 2020-2021

Number of Training Days	Frequency	Percentage Distribution (%)
5 – 8	21	29.17
9 – 12	48	66.67
13 – 16	3	4.16
Total	72	100.00

The table above shows that 66.67 percent of the respondents had 9 to 12 training days in the English language in the school year 2020 to 2021. This idea implies that teachers should undergo more training relevant to English. Moreover, teachers' training was necessary to employ proper methods of teaching. Based on the result of the study conducted in Spain on the utilization of instructional materials, it is recommended that teachers continue to undergo training, workshops, and advanced studies to capacitate themselves in employing the tools appropriately (Bukoye, 2019).

2. Extent of English Teachers' Use of Instructional Materials

The extent of use of English teachers of instructional materials was determined in this study. This involved the printed, audio, visual, audio-visual, and teacher-made resources.

Table 2.1 Printed

Resources	Weighted Mean	Adjectival Rating
Magazine	2.53	Very Seldom
Newspaper	2.57	Very Seldom
Textbook	4.58	Very Much
Photographs	3.19	Seldom
Activity Sheets	4.68	Very Much
Posters	2.90	Seldom
Tarp	2.78	Seldom
Handouts	3.82	Much
Mean	3.38	Seldom

Adjectival Rating Equivalences:

4.21 – 5.00 – Very Much 3.41 – 4.20 - Much 2.61 – 3.40 - Seldom 1.81 – 2.60 – Very Seldom
 1.00 – 1.80 – Not Used at All

Table 2.1 shows that the respondents seldom used printed instructional materials, as demonstrated by the weighted mean of 3.38. This idea implies that Printed resources are used 2 to 3 times a week. Impressively, they used many activity sheets, as shown by the weighted mean of 4.68. On the other hand, they used Very Seldom the Magazine, as exhibited by the Weighted Mean of 2.53. Moreover, the study, Activities of Students in Using Worksheet Based on Contextual Teaching and Learning, is pertinent to this outcome. The findings showed that using student worksheets based on contextual teaching and learning improves students' comprehension of the subject matter (Fauziah & Nurita, 2019).

2.2 Audio

Resources	Weighted Mean	Adjectival Rating
Tape Recorder	2.08	Very Seldom
Radio	1.92	Very Seldom
Cellphone	4.33	Very Much
Record Player	3.07	Seldom
Composite Mean	2.85	Seldom

Adjectival Rating Equivalences:

4.21 – 5.00 – Very Much 3.41 – 4.20 – Much 2.61 – 3.40 – Seldom 1.81 – 2.60 – Very Seldom
 1.00 – 1.80 – Not Used at All

The table above presents that the respondents Seldom used Audio, as exhibited by the Composite Mean of 2.85. This means that Audio is used 2 to 3 times a week. Appreciatively, Very Much use of cell phones was practiced, as evidenced by the Weighted Mean of 4.33, while Radio was Very Seldom used, as evidenced by the Weighted Mean of 1.92. This is because students' usage of cell phones might cause them to get disengaged from the lecture, which can result in worse grades (Buccino, 2018). In addition, based on respondents' experience, respondents limit the activities requiring cell phones since other students do not, especially those living in the hinterland.

2.3 Visual

Resources	Weighted Mean	Adjectival Rating
Realia (Real Objects)	3.54	Much
Chalkboard	2.76	Seldom
Bulletin Board	2.38	Very Seldom
Flannel Story Board	3.21	Seldom
Handouts	4.13	Much
PowerPoint	4.43	Very Much
Still Pictures	3.60	Much
Flashcards	3.22	Seldom
Composite Mean	3.41	Much

Adjectival Rating Equivalences:

4.21 – 5.00 – Very Much 3.41 – 4.20 – Much 2.61 – 3.40 – Seldom 1.81 – 2.60 – Very Seldom
 1.00 – 1.80 – Not Used at All

The table above exposes that Much use of Visual was done by the respondents using Handouts, Still Pictures, and Realia (Real Objects) as evidenced by the Weighted Mean of 3.41 and Weighted Means of 4.13, 3.60, and 3.54 respectively. This connotes that Visual is used four to 5 times a week. Surprisingly, seldom use of a Bulletin Board

was initiated as exhibited by the Weighted Mean of 2.38. Relevantly, according to the study titled Activities of Students in Using Worksheets Based on Contextual Teaching and Learning, using student worksheets based on contextual teaching and learning improves students' comprehension of the subject matter (Fauziah & Nurita, 2019).

2.4 Audio-Visual

Resources	Weighted Mean	Adjectival Rating
Television	3.90	Much
Film	3.22	Seldom
Projector	3.42	Much
Laptop	4.51	Very Much
Composite Mean	3.76	Much

Adjectival Rating Equivalences:

4.21 – 5.00 – Very Much 3.41 – 4.20 - Much 2.61 – 3.40 - Seldom 1.81 – 2.60 – Very Seldom
 1.00 – 1.80 – Not Used at All

The table above shows that Much use of Audio-Visual was done as exposed by the Weighted Mean of 3.76. This indicates that Audio-Visual is used four to 5 times a week. While the Laptop was Very Much used, as shown by the Weighted Mean of 4.51, Film was Seldom used, as demonstrated by the Weighted Mean of 3.22. Laptops are useful for helping students sharpen their writing. Once students have mastered typing, they can "write" more quickly on a computer than by hand. It is also easier to find faults and make fixes when integrated grammar and spelling checkers and thesauruses are used. Students can examine their papers for plagiarism even after they are finished (Zadvinskis, 2022). Additionally, it can help students become computer-savvy. Individuals will likely increase their computer literacy by participating in more practical computer activities (the theory of cone of experience). The research titled "Students Computer Literacy and Academic Performance" found that students' academic performance improved as their computer literacy increased (Cadiz-Gabejan & Takenaka, 2021). Moreover, the teachers use laptops because of their portability. Since they are so small, laptops are quite portable. They can easily move from one place to another in a carrying case or backpack. They are, therefore, efficient tools that teachers may carry with them wherever they go (Bhattacharya, 2021). In addition, teachers use laptops since they are useful for their jobs, particularly reviewing and grading students (Street, 2017).

2.5 Teacher-made Resources

Resources	Weighted Mean	Adjectival Rating
SIM (Strategic Intervention Material)	3.04	Seldom
Assessment tool	4.25	Very Much
Vocabulary or word walls	3.88	Much
Flannel storyboard	2.90	Seldom
Posters	3.03	Seldom
Lesson plans	4.64	Very much
Spelling Lists	3.68	Much
Activity Sheets	4.43	Very much
Composite Mean	3.73	Much

Adjectival Rating Equivalences:

4.21 – 5.00 – Very Much 3.41 – 4.20 - Much 2.61 – 3.40 - Seldom 1.81 – 2.60 – Very Seldom
 1.00 – 1.80 – Not Used at All

The table above presents that the respondents used Teacher-made Resources as exposed by the composite Mean of 3.73. This means that the Teacher-made Resources are used four to 5 times a week. Furthermore, they used Very Much the Activity Sheets as shown by the Weighted Mean of 4.43, and Seldom used the Flannel storyboard as indicated by the Weighted Mean of 2.90. Furthermore, based on the result of the study titled, Students can easily relate the activity sheets and with the use of assessment tools, they can gauge the learning of the students. Students' understanding of the subject matter is improved by employing worksheets based on contextual teaching and learning (Fauziah & Nurita, 2019).

Table 2.6 Summary of Use of Instructional Materials

Instructional Materials	Mean of Weighted Means	Adjectival Rating
Printed	3.38	Seldom
Audio	2.85	Seldom
Visual	3.41	Much
Audio-Visual	3.76	Much
Teacher-made Resources	3.73	Much
Composite Mean	3.43	Much

Adjectival Rating Equivalences:

4.21 – 5.00 – Very Much 3.41 – 4.20 - Much 2.61 – 3.40 - Seldom 1.81 – 2.60 – Very Seldom
 1.00 – 1.80 – Not Used at All

The summary presents that Much use of the Instructional Materials was done by the respondents specifically in the use of Audio-Visual, Teacher-made Resources, and Visual as demonstrated by the Composite Weighted Means of 3.43 and Weighted Means of 3.76, 3.73, and 3.41 respectively. This implies that the Instructional Materials are used four to 5 times a week. Besides, they Seldom Used Printed and Audio Instructional Materials as shown by the Weighted Means of 3.38 and 2.85 respectively. According to studies, using audio-visual resources in the classroom significantly benefits learners in grasping difficult subjects. These tools help the students understand these ideas quickly and simply. The most recent technological developments give teachers a lot of possibilities to simplify their tasks. The use of audio-visual aids in class planning has become more common among educators all around the world as a result (Prajapati, 2020).

3. Extent of English Teacher's Availability of Instructional Materials

The extent of English teachers' availability of instructional materials such as print, audio, visual, audiovisual, and teacher-made resources was also determined in this study.

Resources	Weighted Mean	Adjectival Rating
Magazine	2.38	Seldom
Newspaper	2.67	Sometimes
Textbook	4.17	Often
Photographs	3.07	Sometimes

Activity Sheets	4.54	Always
Posters	2.75	Sometimes
Tarp	2.81	Sometimes
Handouts	4.04	Often
Composite Mean	3.30	Sometimes

Table 3.1 Printed

Adjectival Rating Equivalences:

4.21 – 5.00 – Always 3.41 – 4.20 - Often 2.61 – 3.40 - Sometimes 1.81 – 2.60 – Seldom
1.00 – 1.80 – Never

Table 3.1 above shows that Printed Instructional Materials are Sometimes available as demonstrated by the Composite Mean of 3.30. This implies that Printed Instructional Materials are available for use once a week. Impressively, Activity Sheets were Always available as presented by the Weighted Mean of 4.54. But magazine was Seldom used as presented by the Weighted Mean of 2.38. Substantially, this result is similar to the study titled, Activities of Students in Using Worksheet based on Contextual Teaching and Learning. The result revealed that the employment of student worksheets based on contextual teaching and learning increases students' understanding of the material (Fauziah & Nurita, 2019). Furthermore, the use of formative and summative assessments, contextualized or localized, can help both teachers and students. Teachers can measure the performance of the students and be guided to what skills and knowledge be improved. To the students, it can also help them self-assess their performance for improvement and maintenance of good practice (Benefits of Using Summative and Formative Assessments in ESL Classrooms, 2022).

Table 3.2 Audio

Resources	Weighted Mean	Adjectival Rating
Tape Recorder	2.26	Seldom
Radio	2.18	Seldom
Cellphone	3.89	Often
Record Player	3.22	Sometimes
Composite Mean	2.89	Sometimes

Adjectival Rating Equivalences:

4.21 – 5.00 – Always 3.41 – 4.20 - Often 2.61 – 3.40 - Sometimes 1.81 – 2.60 – Seldom
1.00 – 1.80 – Never

The table above presents that the Audio was Sometimes available as exhibited by the Weighted Mean of 2.89. This indicates that the Audio was available for use once a week. However, the cell phone was Often available as exhibited by the Weighted Mean of 3.89, and Radio was Seldom available as reflected by the Weighted Mean of 2.18. When teachers use cell phones as instructional material in the class, students also get to use this thing to relate to and experience the task (theory of Cone of Experience). Nevertheless, students' use of cellphone can distract their attention from learning the lesson and can lead to lower grades (Buccino, 2018). Another, when it comes to

experience, English teachers corroborated that if cell phones can be part of learning a lesson, it would be unequal to those students who cannot afford to buy cell phones for their classes. Thus, the goal of teaching-learning can be compromised. Relatively, radio was seldom used. One of the reasons why teachers seldom use radio is because many devices like laptops and televisions can offer more experience than using radio. Radio alone can just target the auditory sense of the learners while laptops and television both cater to the audio-visual senses. Hearing only has 20% of remembering while hearing and seeing has 50% which is evident in the audio-visual materials (Janoska, 2021).

Table 3.3 Visual

Resources	Weighted Mean	Adjectival Rating
Realia (Real Objects)	3.63	Often
Chalkboard	4.00	Often
Bulletin Board	3.56	Often
Flannel Story Board	3.01	Sometimes
Handouts	4.11	Often
PowerPoint	4.39	Always
Still Pictures	3.56	Often
Flashcards	3.36	Sometimes
Composite Mean	3.70	Often

Adjectival Rating Equivalences:

4.21 – 5.00 – Always 3.41 – 4.20 - Often 2.61 – 3.40 - Sometimes 1.81 – 2.60 – Seldom
 1.00 – 1.80 – Never

The table above exposes that Visual was Often Available as exhibited by the composite mean of 3.70. This connotes that Visual was available for use twice a week. Favorably, PowerPoint was Always available as proven by the Weighted Mean of 4.39. On the other hand, Flannel storyboard was Sometimes available as evidenced by the Weighted Mean of 3.01. substantially, the use of PowerPoint is essential in engaging students to participate in class discussions. The PowerPoint presentations had a great impact on pupils because they believed it was entertaining and interesting to follow the lesson from the screen. The use of PowerPoint encourages pupils to attend class. (Effects of PowerPoint Presentation in the Academic Performance, 2022). This is just one of the positive effects of utilizing PowerPoint presentations. Teachers utilize this for the better conveyance of ideas. Likely, when communication is supplied through several channels, it is more effective than communication that is done through only one. It increases the likelihood that the entire message will be received by using many channels. A suitable image adds a new channel. Thus, the use of PowerPoint can motivate learners and provide better interaction with teachers (Pros and Cons Teaching via PowerPoint, 2021).

Table 3.4 Audio-Visual

Resources	Weighted Mean	Adjectival Rating
Television	3.93	Often
Film	2.93	Sometimes
Projector	3.03	Sometimes
Laptop	4.49	Always

Composite Mean	3.60	Often
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Adjectival Rating Equivalences

4.21 – 5.00 – Always 3.41 – 4.20 - Often 2.61 – 3.40 - Sometimes 1.81 – 2.60 – Seldom
 1.00 – 1.80 – Never

The table above displays that the Audio-Visual was Often available as exhibited by the Composite Mean of 3.60. This means that the Audio-Visual is available twice a week. Moreover, the Laptop was Always available as evidenced by the Weighted Mean of 4.49 but the Film was Sometimes available as exposed by the Weighted Mean of 2.93. When it comes to assisting learners in improving their writing, laptops are helpful. Once learners master typing, they can "write" on a computer more quickly than by hand. Using integrated grammar and spelling checkers and thesauruses also makes it simpler to spot errors and make corrections. Even after finishing their papers, students can check them for plagiarism (Zadvinskis, 2022). Also, it can improve the computer skills of the learners. The more they engage in hands-on computer activities (theory of cone of experience), the higher the opportunity to improve their computer literacy. A study titled, Students Computer Literacy and Academic Performance, revealed that the more computer-literate students were, the better they performed academically (Cadiz-Gabejan & Takenaka, 2021). As for the teachers, they utilize laptops due to their portability. Laptops are extremely portable due to their small size. In a carrying case or backpack, they are simple to transport from one location to another. Because of this, they are handy items that teachers can take wherever they go (Bhattacharya, 2021). Aside from this, teachers utilize laptops because it is useful in performing their tasks, especially reviewing and giving grades to their students (Street, 2017).

Table 3.5 Teacher-made Resources

Resources	Weighted Mean	Adjectival Rating
SIM (Strategic Intervention Material)	3.10	Sometimes
Assessment tool	4.21	Always
Vocabulary or word walls	3.44	Often
Flannel storyboard	2.82	Sometimes
Posters	3.08	Sometimes
Lesson plans	4.86	Always
Spelling Lists	3.68	Often
Activity Sheets	4.33	Often
Mean	3.69	Often

Adjectival Rating Equivalences:

4.21 – 5.00 – Always 3.41 – 4.20 - Often 2.61 – 3.40 - Sometimes 1.81 – 2.60 – Seldom
 1.00 – 1.80 – Never

The table above exposes that Teacher-made Resources were Often Available as proven by the Weighted Mean of 3.69. This indicates that the Teacher-made Resources are available for use twice a week. Impressively, Lesson Plans were Always Available as exhibited by the Weighted Mean of 4.86 but the Flannel storyboard is Sometimes available as indicated by the Weighted Mean of 2.82. Substantially, lesson plan guides teachers in delivering the lesson. Teachers combine their understanding of their teaching

situation, methodology, and curriculum goals as part of lesson planning (The Importance of Lesson Planning for Student Success, 2022). Amidst the pandemic, according to the Department of Education, teachers in public schools would still be required to create daily lesson plans and logs to guarantee high-quality instruction. The government stated in a statement that using a DLL (Daily Lesson Log) "supports teachers in upholding quality education standards and helps them plan lessons efficiently and effectively" (PNA, 2022).

Table 3.6 Summary of Use of Instructional Materials

Instructional Materials	Mean of Weighted Means	Adjectival Rating
Printed	3.30	Sometimes
Audio	2.89	Sometimes
Visual	3.70	Often
Audio-Visual	3.60	Often
Teacher-made Resources	3.69	Often
Composite	3.44	Often

Adjectival Rating Equivalences:

4.21 – 5.00 – Always 3.41 – 4.20 - Often 2.61 – 3.40 - Sometimes 1.81 – 2.60 – Seldom
1.00 – 1.80 – Never

The summary shows that the Instructional Materials were Often Available as exhibited by the Composite Mean of 3.44. This implies that the Instructional Materials are available for use twice a week. Moreover, Visual is Often Available as provided by the Weighted Mean of 3.70 but Audio is Sometimes Available as exhibited by the Weighted Mean of 2.89. This is supported by the responses of the teachers in FGD. According to them, they utilized handouts, activity sheets, and PowerPoint presentations because they observed how students reacted and interacted with teachers in class discussions. A study titled Investigating EFL Students' Attitude toward the Use of Visual Aids in English Lectures revealed that students had a positive attitude toward the use of visual aids in English class (Aljuhani & Maroof, 2019). Further, during FGD, teachers also said that audio was sometimes available but not all the time, English lessons require them to use audio materials. Some visual learners are not comfortable with the input provided by the audio material and prefer to see the images. Plus, it would be hard for students to comprehend and explain abstract concepts through audio format only (Disadvantages of Audio Technologies, n.d.).

4. Relationship Between the Instructional Materials Used by English Teachers and their Demographic Profile

The relationship between the extent of instructional materials used by English Teachers and the demographic profile such as age, highest educational attainment, teachers' performance rating, and number of training days were determined using Pearson R and Spearman Rho Correlation.

Table 4.1 Correlation Between the Instructional Materials Used by English Teachers and their Demographic Profile

Variables Correlated with Extent Use of Instructional Materials	Correlational Tool Used	Correlation Coefficient	P-Value
Age	Pearson R	0.224	0.058
Highest Educational Attainment	Spearman Rho	-0.257	0.030
Teachers Performance Rating	Spearman Rho	-0.054	0.651
Number of Training Days	Pearson R	-0.005	0.964

As reflected in the table above, Age and Highest Educational Attainment had weak correlations with the Extent of Use of Instructional Material as presented by the correlation of 0.224 and -0.257 respectively. Furthermore, the latter was significant as demonstrated by the P-value of 0.030 at 0.05 level. This implies that the higher the educational level the teacher has, the lesser he/she uses the Instructional Materials.

5. Relationship Between the Extent Use and Availability of Instructional Materials Utilized by English Teachers

The relationship between the extent of use and availability of instructional materials was determined using Pearson R Correlation.

Table 5.1 Correlation Between the Extent Use and Availability of Instructional Materials Utilized by English Teachers

Extent of Use of Instructional Materials Correlated with Availability of Instructional Materials	Correlational Tool Used	Correlation Coefficient	P-Value
	Pearson R	0.566	0.000

As shown by the table above Extent of use of Instructional Materials has a medium association with the Availability of Instructional Materials as exhibited by the Correlation Coefficient of 0.566 and is highly significant as evidenced by the P-Value of 0.000 at 0.05 level. This indicates that the higher the Instructional Materials the more available they are and vice versa.

6. Difference Between the Availability and the Extent of Use of Instructional Materials when Respondents are Grouped According to Location

The difference between the availability and the extent of use of instructional materials, when respondents are grouped according to location, was determined using T-Test at a 5% significance level.

Table 6.1 T-Test in Finding the Significant Difference Between the Availability and the Extent of Use of Instructional Materials when Respondents are Grouped According to Location.

Location	Use of Instructional Materials			Availability of Instructional Materials		
	Mean	p-value	Interpretation	Mean	P-Value	Interpretation
Low Land	3.38	0.150	Significant	3.38	0.652	Significant
High Land	3.58			3.40		

The table above shows that Instructional Materials in Highland Location are Used more than in Low Land as presented by the means of 3.58 and 3.38 respectively. This difference is proven significant as shown by the p-value of 0.150. This implies that teachers and students in Highland Locations can utilize more of the Instructional Materials than in Low Land Locations. This is because, some of the students in the hinterland do not have gadgets which led teachers to be creative and resourceful to employ a variety of instructional materials like printed, and audio, and limited use of visual, audiovisual, and even developed materials to cater the needs of the learners. On the other hand, teachers in low-income schools prefer ICTs in teaching to using traditional instructional materials because it can make their tasks easier and more productive. Aside from this, their students have gadgets, and they prefer modern ways of teaching the learning process (How Important Is Technology in Education? Benefits, Challenges, and Impact on Students, 2020). There are also more available instructional materials in the highland location than in the lowlands as exhibited by the means of 3.40 and 3.38 respectively. Said difference is significant as manifested by the p-value of 0.652. This indicated that varied instructional materials in land locations are more available than in lowland Locations.

Table 7. Thematic map of English teachers' experiences in utilizing instructional materials

Codes	Themes
Power interruption Students have no devices No signal in students' residence Cannot understand the medium of instruction in modules Teachers' lack of training Provision of parallel activities Translating English to Vernacular Contextualizing and localizing materials	Challenges amidst crisis Best practices amidst challenges

Challenges Amidst Crisis

When using instructional materials, English teachers in schools in the hinterland confront many difficulties. A significant obstacle is the need for more current and pertinent resources. It is difficult for many schools in rural locations to get textbooks, workbooks, and other supplies essential for efficient teaching and learning. This may make it more difficult for educators to provide learners with engaging lessons and teaching. The major problem for teachers pertains to power interruption whenever using audio-visual materials such as TVs, speakers, laptops for PowerPoint presentations, and projectors. In this regard, educators and students in a virtual classroom would require vital e-learning technologies that require continuous electricity to keep them functioning and avoid problems that could obstruct the students' learning experience (Castillo, 2021). Thus, it is important to identify problems that impede learning and take action to achieve learning goals (Fons, 2022), explained by the constraint theory. Moreover, another problem is the need for more possibilities for professional growth and training for English instructors in rural schools has been another problem. Teachers could find it easier to incorporate educational resources into their courses if they can access continuing support and advice. This might result in inconsistent teaching methods and make it harder to satisfy the various demands of the pupils. English teachers in schools in the hinterland often have to deal with a need for digital infrastructure. Reliable internet connectivity, computers, and other technical equipment are necessary to access digital resources and integrate multimedia into lectures, yet they sometimes need improvement in distant places. The statements of the participants support this event.

Respondent 4 said,

“Since I am teaching in a hinterland school, we experience a lack of devices and high-end technology-mediated materials. This prompted me to utilize a variety of materials like activity sheets, lesson plans, and customized and localized materials. also, I don’t know how to use other techniques in the employment of other materials since I lack training on it.”

Moreover, respondent 3 added,

“I agree. Most of the time, I used a variety of materials since we majority of our students cannot relate due to the absence of gadgets. Also, in the school, we don’t have an internet connection in school, and we always experience power interruptions.”

Respondent 1 added,

“Unlike in our school, since we are in urban areas, internet connection is available. So, most of the time I used a laptop, cellphones, power point presentations since these are available in our context.”

Respondent 5 added,

“We’re the same. Our students have cell phones and the internet is also available in our school. We can just send templates for activity sheets or even assignments to our

students. for the delivery of the lesson, I always use PowerPoint presentations since it helps a lot in stimulating my students' mood and they perform better with it.”

Responded 6 answered,

“On the other hand, in my case, since I am teaching in the hinterland, I found it challenging to use ICT-related materials and devices. Although I use a laptop sometimes, it is not reliable since it has a small screen. We also don't have an internet connection, so we don't have much use for live online surfing. In delivering the lessons in my subject, I always use meta strips and localized materials.”

Respondent 2 highlighted,

“I am a teacher in a lowland school, but we don't have an internet connection. But have TVs and a projector that we can use to present our lessons for the day. PowerPoint presentation amazes our learners but only simple presentations I can afford to do since I am not trained to use other teaching I also use activity sheets and assessment tools. Somehow, these aid me in assessing my students' performance. But most of the time, I used ICT-related instructional materials.”

Lastly, respondent 7 said,

“There in the hinterland, we always used printed materials and other teacher-made resources since we didn't have an internet connection. I always use activity sheets, lesson plans, and assessment tools.”

Utilizing instructional materials presents a big problem for English teachers working in rural schools. As expressed by the hinterland respondents, they have limited use of ICT-related materials since it is not convenient in their context. With this, Policymakers, school administrators, and teacher preparation programs must make it a top priority to provide teachers working in rural locations with sufficient resources, chances for professional development, and digital infrastructure. We cannot guarantee that all kids, regardless of where they live, have access to high-quality English instruction until we address these problems.

Best Practices Amidst Challenges

English teachers are essential in helping learners become more proficient in the language and literacy. Using the right teaching resources is one of the main elements of a good teaching strategy. To optimize learning outcomes, English teachers must use best practices when utilizing these materials, even when students have differing levels of comprehension in the modules. In this pandemic, students found it hard to comprehend the module content since modules are not localized and contextualized. This prompted the teachers to be innovative and resourceful in addressing learning issues for learners. The statements of the respondents substantiate this phenomenon.

Respondent 3 said,

“I always receive complaints from my students that they don’t understand what’s inside of the modules since the language of instruction English is. Moreover, they found the activities irrelevant in their context.”

Respondent 7 added,

“In my case, I always make a point to read the module first then knowing the background knowledge of my students, I made parallel activities and localized my materials for my students to connect. I even translated the language into vernacular so they can understand better.”

Respondent 4 stressed,

“Localizing materials is the best strategy I can employ. Modules were challenging for them, so I needed to localize and translate them for better understanding. I also made parallel activities just in case they cannot answer what’s in the modules.”

Respondent 6 answered,

“Most of the reported problems of my students is that the words or vocabulary used in the modules were a bit hard to understand. So, I read first the module, and I made a parallel activity for them, a simpler version of the modules yet still targeting the competencies and objectives of the lesson.”

Moreover, respondent 1 said,

“Sometimes, I make a simple activity and attach it to the modules. There, students are guided with what to do on the given task.”

Furthermore, respondent 2 answered,

“What I did is that I translated the difficult words and replaced them with easier ones for my students to understand. Moreover, there were times when I made localized materials like parallel activities to make sure that they could relate and use materials that are found in their surroundings.”

Lastly, respondent 5 emphasized,

“I agree with all they said, even when students have gadgets and others may have them, the absence of an instructor makes them receive education quite difficult. So, I always make sure the activities are well-reviewed before distributing them to my students. I make parallel activities a simpler version of the module. Through this, they can still achieve their objectives.”

Effective teaching in English can be hard to attain when there limiting factors that impede the teaching-learning process. This includes teachers’ utilization of instructional materials. As expressed by the respondents, it is evident that they encounter challenges such as the unavailability of the materials due to their residence’s resources, and students’ difficulty in dealing with modules during the pandemic time. However, teachers demonstrated innovative characteristics to address this rising crisis by creating parallel activities, localizing materials for the students to connect and relate, and translating and

replacing difficult words with simpler versions. These acts are considered best practices of teachers in the lowlands and hinterland.

Conclusion

The findings of this study concluded that with many teachers in their 30s, where the majority acquired insufficient pieces of training and were unable to finish advanced studies, they perform better with much use of the Instructional Materials four to 5 times a week for 4 to 5 subjects and often available or used twice a week. Furthermore, the higher the Instructional Materials used, the more available they are, and vice versa, though teachers with higher education tend to lessen the use of Instructional Materials. Thus, the Use and Availability of Instructional Materials can help enhance students learning, especially when they do tasks that involve the utilization of these materials (Theory of Cone of Experience), and they can associate their experiences by connecting to the new sets of ideas and concepts (Theory of Connectionism). Further, the result also showed that English teachers experience challenges, including power interruption, especially when using laptops, TVs, power points, speakers, and projectors. Despite this, English teachers kept using these tools to help improve the students' academic performance. Also, teachers find it difficult to use modules since the contents are not localized, and students find it hard to understand the language, instructions, and content. However, this does not hinder English teachers from stopping teaching; instead, teachers have made parallel activities that are localized and simplified. Moreover, more instructional materials are used and available in the Highlands than in lowland locations.

Furthermore, this study recommends that teachers undergo training to better utilize instructional materials in addressing diverse learners. Moreover, DepEd must intensify the provision of instructional materials to teachers for a greater chance of availability. School administrators and school heads must encourage and support the needs of their teachers, especially in terms of instructional materials. For future researchers, using different variables in instructional materials can be a good focus for the next study. You can use a comparative analysis technique to determine the difference in the availability and extent of use of these materials and compare them to the setup of the new normal setting.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher hereby certifies that the study was carried out with caution and ethics. The researchers requested consent from the division office of the school in writing before the study's actual implementation. The researchers invited the potential volunteers to an orientation after they were approved. The researchers invited the potential volunteers to an orientation after they were granted approval. The study's nature and objectives, informed consent, participant anonymity, data confidentiality, and withdrawal rights were all on the agenda. The potential participants comprehended all these explanations. As a result, the participants signed the informed consent and indicated their support. Additionally, the sources cited in this research are appropriately recognized, and the study is free from plagiarism.

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